

Spiking Neural Networks for Noise-Robust Walk-in-Place Navigation in VR: An Image-Based Encoding of Positional Data

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Abstract

Classifying walking-in-place (WIP) states in virtual reality (VR) as a method for locomotion through extended virtual environments remains a critical challenge for enhancing immersion and interaction. This paper addresses WIP navigation by converting motion sensor data—captured from VR headsets and controllers, including head and hand movements—into 2D images for neural network-based classification. We evaluate two approaches: a traditional artificial neural network based on the multilayer perceptron (MLP) and a neuromorphic model inspired by biological principles, specifically the resonate-and-fire (RAF) neuron. Our findings demonstrate three key contributions. First, encoding sensor data into images effectively preserves movement history while reducing the complexity associated with raw coordinate processing. Second, we show that simple neural models can accurately classify WIP states in real-time, achieving up to 99.87% accuracy with an MLP and 98.57% with a spiking RAF network. Third, our comparative analysis reveals that the neuromorphic RAF model exhibits superior noise robustness and potential for greater energy efficiency.

Furthermore, a user study involving 30 participants evaluated our neural network approach against a traditional head-analysis WIP baseline and Teleport locomotion. While Teleport was preferred for overall navigation ease, our method demonstrated significantly improved classification performance and was clearly

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preferred by users over the baseline head-analysis WIP method validating its effectiveness as an enhanced WIP solution. We conclude that combining image-based sensor encoding with efficient neural classifiers offers a robust solution for WIP state discrimination in VR, with potential extensions to other motion-based interaction tasks.

Keywords: Virtual reality (VR), walking-in-place (WIP), artificial neural networks (ANNs), spiking neural networks (SNNs), resonate-and-fire neuron (RAF)

1 Introduction

Walking-in-place (WIP) has emerged as an effective strategy for addressing the inherent limitations of conventional navigation methods in virtual reality (VR) environments, enabling participants to explore virtual worlds that exceed the boundaries of their physical space. Traditional input devices—such as joysticks, trackpads, and treadmills—often fail to replicate the multisensory cues of real walking, creating a perceptual disconnect between the participant’s bodily actions and the locomotion through the virtual environment, thus leading to conflicts between the visual and vestibular senses that produce participant discomfort, reduced immersion, and the well-documented risk of motion (simulator) sickness [1–6].

WIP, by contrast, allows participants to remain physically in one location while simulating walking motions. In doing so, it better aligns vestibular and proprioceptive feedback (the sense of the relative position and movement of the body) with visual input, resulting in more natural and comfortable VR locomotion [7–10], which, in turn, has been shown to reduce motion sickness through viewpoint oscillations [11, 12].

Despite its promise, implementing robust WIP-based locomotion poses a significant challenge: reliably identifying when a participant is actually engaged in walking-in-place versus other actions or idle movements. This classification step is crucial for ensuring a realistic navigation of virtual spaces, reducing sensorimotor incongruities, and enhancing participant presence. Classical threshold-based detection—such as head-bob sensing—provides a simple but often inconsistent solution, as it may fail to account for individual gait styles, random head movements, or noisy sensor data. Consequently, the overarching research question driving this work is whether we can create a computationally efficient classification system, robust to noise and individual variability, that reliably detects WIP states in real-time?

To address this question, we propose a novel solution that leverages simple neural network models, including Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs) and MultiLayer Perceptrons (MLPs), for WIP detection. Specifically, we introduce a 2D image-encoding scheme that converts three-dimensional positional data (head and hand movements) into compact images suitable for classification. By transforming raw sensor signals into a more structured, image-based representation, our approach not only preserves key motion features but also streamlines feature extraction—thereby enabling minimal neural network architectures to achieve high performance with reduced computational overhead. Furthermore, this approach optimizes for real-time inference, which is vital

for interactive VR scenarios. We validated our method on data from 15 participants with varying movement styles, ensuring the robustness of our proposed approach to individual differences.

In addition to tackling the fundamental detection challenge, we also investigated how both traditional neural networks and neuromorphic models perform in this classification task. Critically, our findings demonstrate practical benefits for low-power, real-time VR systems, making these methods suitable for standalone headsets and edge devices with constrained resources. Moreover, robust WIP classification can enhance immersion in a wide range of VR applications—from entertainment to rehabilitation—where naturalistic locomotion significantly improves participant outcomes.

1.1 Contributions

This paper makes the following key contributions:

1. **Novel 2D Encoding of VR Motion.** We present a flexible technique for converting 3D head-and-hand tracking data into 2D image representations, effectively capturing spatial and temporal motion cues without complex raw-coordinate processing.
2. **Comparison of Traditional and Neuromorphic Models.** We systematically evaluate both conventional MLPs and a RAF spiking neural network. Our results demonstrate that neuromorphic architectures can match—or surpass—classical ANNs in WIP classification accuracy, particularly under noisy conditions.
3. **Minimal Architecture, High Accuracy.** We show that even single-layer networks with few neurons achieve over 95% classification accuracy in WIP detection. This finding underscores the feasibility of deploying lightweight solutions in real-time VR applications.
4. **Robustness to Sensor Noise.** By introducing synthetic noise during testing, we illustrate that spiking-based models offer enhanced resilience to perturbations. This suggests their viability for real-world VR environments where sensor signals are imperfect.

Together, these contributions advance the state of the art in WIP classification for VR, bridging insights from classical AI methods and biologically inspired spiking architectures. Our approach paves the way for improved participant experience in various VR contexts, from immersive gaming to therapeutic simulations.

1.2 Related Work

Numerous approaches have been proposed for locomotion through virtual environments, leveraging participant body movements, external peripherals, or a combination of both [13]. This section reviews the main categories, including traditional locomotion methods, body-driven techniques like WIP, and emerging machine learning and neuromorphic paradigms.

1.2.1 Traditional Locomotion Methods

Traditional locomotion methods, such as handheld controllers where the user teleports to another location by point-and-click, have been extensively studied. Although they provide precise motion control, these systems often fail to replicate the natural walking experience, leading to reduced immersion and usability challenges [13]. Semi-natural solutions like omnidirectional treadmills offer high fidelity in motion tracking and afford real walking movements, but their high cost, physical effort requirements, and cumbersome setup often limit their practicality [14, 15]. Conversely, point-and-teleport methods enable quick navigation and reduce motion sickness but disrupt spatial continuity and presence [16, 17]. These limitations highlight the need for more intuitive and cost-effective locomotion systems.

1.2.2 WIP Techniques

Walking-in-Place (WIP) leverages participants’ physical movements to simulate walking within virtual reality (VR) environments. The technique was first proposed by Slater *et al.* [9, 18], initially termed “walking on the spot” and was first implemented employing feed-forward neural networks for head-tracking data analysis. Early and subsequent research increasingly employed machine learning methods based on neural networks to address the complexities of reliably identifying WIP states. Usoh *et al.* [7] extended Slater *et al.* work to compare WIP with real walking dynamics. More recently, Hanson *et al.* [19] introduced convolutional neural networks (CNNs) specifically tailored for real-time WIP detection, demonstrating improved robustness over simpler models. Despite these advances, even sophisticated neural network approaches relying on raw or minimally processed signals can face challenges regarding adaptability to varying movement patterns and resilience to noise prevalent in dynamic VR environments.

Alongside these network-based methods, simpler threshold-based approaches have also emerged by analyzing data directly from sensors to identify predefined patterns associated with WIP. For instance, Lee *et al.* [20] proposed detecting characteristic variations in head height using VR headset positional data. Similarly, Tregillus and Folmer [21] implemented VR-step, a pedometry-based WIP method relying on inertial sensors, akin to those in smartphones. While computationally less demanding and potentially effective in controlled scenarios, these threshold-based methods often struggle to generalize due to their inherent sensitivity to individual gait differences, sensor noise, and variations in user posture, highlighting the need for the more adaptive learning-based techniques mentioned previously.

1.2.3 Neuromorphic Computing and SNNs

Spiking neural networks (SNNs) offer a biologically inspired alternative to traditional artificial neural networks (ANNs). Unlike ANNs, SNNs process information via discrete spikes, making them inherently suited for time-dependent tasks and energy-efficient computations [22]. Studies suggest that SNNs excel in handling noisy or sparse data [23, 24], which is particularly valuable for VR applications requiring real-time responsiveness. Moreover, neuromorphic hardware platforms, such as Intel’s Loihi and

IBM’s TrueNorth, have demonstrated the feasibility of running spike-based algorithms efficiently [25, 26].

In this context, we introduce a resonate-and-fire (RAF) neuron model for WIP detection, aiming to harness the advantages of neuromorphic intelligence in immersive VR systems. Despite the promise of SNNs, their application to WIP detection remains relatively unexplored, marking a key focus of this paper.

1.3 Proposed Approach

While prior techniques effectively process raw data from position trackers or inertial measurement units (IMUs), relying solely on unprocessed signals can limit their adaptability under varying participant movement patterns or noisy conditions. To address these constraints, we propose a neural network-based approach that automatically detects WIP movements by encoding positional data from three key points of interest: the participant’s head, left hand, and right hand. Specifically, the tracked data from the VR headset and controllers are processed and mapped into 2D images capturing positions across multiple frames. This transformation preserves temporal movement history while mitigating the complexity of raw-coordinate processing, thereby enabling simpler neural network architectures with fewer neuron units. As a result, our method supports real-time classification and reduces overall hardware requirements.

In this work, we compare two neural network paradigms: a traditional MLP-based model and a neuromorphic model inspired by biological systems, exemplified by the resonate-and-fire neuron (RAF). We train and evaluate both models to reliably classify WIP states in real-time, aiming to enhance computational efficiency and participant immersion in VR environments.

The structure of the paper is as follows: Section 2 presents the mathematical foundations of the MLP and SNN models. Section 3 describes the materials used, the proposed method for encoding participant positional tracking data into images, the neural network architectures designed for comparing SNN and MLP models, and the creation of the database for training and testing the networks. Section 4 reports the experimental results obtained. Finally, Sections 6 and 7 provide the discussion and conclusions, respectively.

2 Multi-layer Perceptron and Spiking Neural Network

The development of artificial neural networks (ANNs) marked a significant shift in AI research and applications, moving from explicit rule-based systems to data-driven learning approaches.

The perceptron developed by Frank Rosenblatt marked a significant milestone [27]. Although it has limitations, it is considered the foundational model for understanding neural networks and has paved the way for more complex architectures, such as the MLP, that can solve various nonlinear problems; please refer, for example, to Cybenko’s Universal Approximation Theorem [28].

Recently, spiking neural networks (SNNs) have gained attention for brain-inspired computing and deployed on neuromorphic devices. SNNs represent a class of neural

networks that more closely mimic how biological neurons communicate using spikes or action potentials. Unlike traditional ANNs that operate on continuous values and use activation functions, SNNs process information in discrete events or spikes, making them more suitable for modeling temporal dynamics and real-time processing.

The conceptual foundations for SNNs can be traced back to early work in computational neuroscience. Researchers like Hodgkin and Huxley developed dynamics models in 1952 that described how neurons transmit electrical signals, and their work laid the groundwork for later developments in spiking models [29]. In 2001, Izhikevich introduced the resonate-and-fire (RAF) neuron as an alternative to the Hodgkin-Huxley neuron. Izhikevich chose this approach because, although the Hodgkin-Huxley model is more biologically realistic, it can be computationally inefficient when simulating large networks of spiking neurons.

Here we apply these methods to the problem of moving through a VR environment, more specifically in WIP discrimination, presenting a thorough investigation of the capabilities of artificial neural networks that utilize perceptrons and SNNs featuring RAF neurons. By exploring these advanced architectures, we aim to underscore their potential to significantly enhance WIP discrimination performance. We highlight the advantages of using one paradigm or the other to pave the way for future uses in other discriminative tasks within the field of VR.

2.1 The perceptron model

The perceptron takes a vector of input features, often denoted as $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$. Each input is associated with a weight $\mathbf{w} = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)$. The weights determine the importance of each feature in the classification process. An additional parameter, known as the bias, b , is included to allow the decision boundary to shift away from the origin.

The perceptron then computes a weighted sum of the inputs: $z = \mathbf{w} \cdot \mathbf{x} + b = w_1x_1 + w_2x_2 + \dots + w_nx_n + b$, and applies an activation function to the weighted sum. Given that ANNs made up of perceptrons are significantly affected by the choice of activation function, we carefully evaluated three key mathematical expressions: (1) the classic sigmoid function, (2) the hyperbolic tangent, $\tanh()$, and (3) the ReLU function. Each offers unique advantages that can enhance network performance.

The perceptron is trained using labeled data, where each input is associated with a target output. During training, the perceptron adjusts its weights based on the error (the difference between the predicted output and the actual output) using a simple rule: $w_i \leftarrow w_i + \eta(y - \hat{y})x_i$ where η is the learning rate, y is the actual label, and \hat{y} is the predicted label. The bias is also adjusted based on the error: $b \leftarrow b + \eta(y - \hat{y})$.

It is well known that the perceptron can only classify data that is linearly separable, meaning it cannot solve problems where classes cannot be separated by a straight line, and that more complex decision boundaries require MLPs.

Similar expressions can be found for both a single-layer network with n perceptrons and a multi-layer network where each layer consists of n perceptrons.

2.2 The RAF neuron model

The *RAF neuron model* is a neuromorphic framework that more closely mirrors the temporal dynamics and biophysical properties of biological neurons than conventional static units such as perceptrons. Unlike perceptrons, which typically apply a static nonlinear activation function to a weighted sum of inputs, RAF neurons exhibit intrinsically temporal behavior, responding to input stimuli as oscillatory systems that can “resonate” at particular frequencies.

This resonance arises from the neuron’s inherent dynamics, often modeled by a second-order differential equation. A simplified formulation can be expressed as

$$\frac{d^2V}{dt^2} + 2\xi\frac{dV}{dt} + \omega^2V = I_{\text{in}}, \quad (1)$$

where V is the membrane potential, ξ is the damping factor, ω is the angular frequency, and I_{in} is the input to the neuron, for instance, the weighted summation of pre-synaptic spikes. When the input signal’s frequency matches the neuron’s intrinsic resonant frequency, the amplitude of $V(t)$ increases until a threshold V_{th} is reached. At this point, the neuron emits a spike.

This resonant property enables RAF neurons to capture fine-grained temporal patterns and correlations in the input without requiring additional temporal processing mechanisms. Compared to perceptrons, RAF neurons provide several advantages: they support energy-efficient, spike-based communication; they are more robust to noise due to their intrinsic filtering dynamics; and they process temporal signals in a manner that is biologically more plausible and computationally more efficient. These features make RAF neurons particularly appealing for neuromorphic computing architectures, where temporal dynamics, low power consumption, and biological plausibility are paramount.

Since SNNs deal with spikes, which are discontinuous, several approaches have been proposed to enable the efficient training of such networks; for example, see [30]. These can be divided into two folds: the first approach focuses on converting conventional artificial neural networks trained with backpropagation to their spiking counterpart. The second approach involves directly training SNNs on variations of backpropagation. This work falls into the second category. Specifically, we employ the method proposed by [31].

The learnable parameters include the damping factor ξ , the frequency ω , and the neuronal threshold V_{th} . The other adjustable parameters are identical to those of the perceptron, namely the weights \mathbf{w} ; however, the bias b is inherent to the perceptron and does not apply here.

3 Materials and Methods

3.1 Materials

The data for detecting WIP states were acquired from a standard VR setup comprising a head-mounted display (HMD) and two hand-held controllers with built-in positional

tracking. Specifically, we used the Meta Quest 3 [32], a standalone VR headset with the following relevant specifications:

- **Display:** Dual LCD screens with a resolution of 2064×2208 pixels per eye, providing high visual clarity.
- **Refresh Rate:** Operates at 90 Hz, with support for 120 Hz in experimental mode, ensuring smooth transitions and low latency.
- **Field of View (FOV):** Horizontal FOV of 110 degrees and vertical FOV of 96 degrees, enhancing spatial perception in virtual environments.
- **Processor:** Powered by the Qualcomm Snapdragon XR2 Gen 2 chipset, enabling efficient and high-performance VR applications.
- **Memory and Storage:** 8 GB of RAM and 128 GB storage.
- **Tracking and Controllers:** Features dual RGB cameras and a depth projector for precise environmental and controller tracking. Redesigned controllers without tracking rings allow greater freedom of movement and improved accuracy.

These specifications make the Meta Quest 3 an optimal choice for capturing precise motion data and providing an immersive VR experience in the context of this study, particularly due to its consumer-grade accessibility and inside-out tracking capabilities.

The neural network models have been trained in a server with 2 sockets CPU Intel Xeon Silver 4114 CPU @ 2.20GHz with 10 cores per socket, 40 logical processors (threads), 128 GB RAM and a GPU Quadro RTX 6000 with 24 GB VRAM. We used PyTorch (version 1.12.1) and cuda 10.2, taking advantage of GPU acceleration.

3.2 Experimental Setup

A VR environment was designed to resemble a room containing a mirror and an avatar representing the participants. The participants were embodied in this avatar and instructed to perform the WIP movement or other specified actions, as guided by the instructions provided during the experience, to ensure the accurate recording of the samples. For the “non-WIP” class, participants were assigned various tasks, such as grasping virtual objects, pointing, or performing other diverse hand and head movements, to simulate natural interactions within the virtual environment. To visualize the recorded samples, we developed a simple VR scenario featuring a red sphere and two green spheres, representing the recorded movements of the head and hands. Figure 1 shows the visual representation of both VR scenarios.

The system captures the three-dimensional coordinates of the participant’s head, left, and right controller at each frame. To ensure that these measurements are independent of the participant’s absolute position in the virtual environment, we compute all coordinates relative to the avatar’s root position—defined as the vertical projection of the participant’s body center onto the ground plane.

We employ a temporal sliding window of 100 frames to represent each movement sequence. Given that a complete WIP cycle (i.e., the downward and upward motion of both HMD hands during a simulated walking step) lasts approximately one second and the HMD operates at 90 frames per second, this 100-frame window captures slightly

Fig. 1: Visual representation of the VR scenarios.

(a) Snapshot from the avatar’s perspective in the VR scenario used for collecting WIP data. The environment consists of a four-walled room, with task instructions displayed on the front wall.

(b) VR scenario used for visualizing the WIP data. The participant’s head and hands are represented by green and red spheres, respectively. Frontal and lateral views of the position trajectories are shown on the left and right images.

more than one complete WIP cycle. This approach ensures robust temporal coverage and reduces the risk of missing critical motion cues.

We encode the head and hand positional data into a 2D image representation to distinguish WIP movements from other participant actions. Each image corresponds to a 100-frame window and contains information from all three tracked points. The image has a total size of 72 pixels in width and 56 pixels in height and is divided into two distinct halves: 1) The left half, measuring 36 pixels in width by 56 pixels in height, encodes the frontal-plane (X, Y) movements, representing a top-down or front-view projection. 2) The right half, also measuring 36 pixels in width by 56 pixels in height, encodes the depth-plane (Z) movements, enabling visualization of vertical and depth-related dynamics.

Normalizing positional data and mapping these values into image coordinates generates a comprehensive, spatial-temporal representation of the participant’s motion. This visual encoding facilitates downstream analysis, including the training of classification models to distinguish WIP from non-WIP behaviors.

3.2.1 Visualization of Movement Patterns

Figure 2 shows two representative examples from our dataset. Figure 2a corresponds to a WIP movement, while Figure 2b illustrates a non-WIP action. Each image contains two distinct regions:

- **Frontal-plane (X, Y) representation (left half):** This section displays the projection of head and hand movements onto the frontal plane. Three zones can be distinguished: the top-central area corresponds to head movement, the left-central area to the left controller, and the right-central area to the right controller.

- **Depth-plane (Z) representation (right half):** This section encodes vertical and depth-related dynamics. Similar to the frontal plane encoding, three horizontal lines are observed, corresponding to head (upper line), left controller (middle line), and right controller (lower line) movements.

Fig. 2: Examples from the dataset created for WIP detection. Text overlays indicate the spatial zones corresponding to the head and controllers within each image.

3.2.2 Dataset

The dataset was collected from 15 participants, including both men and women aged 23 to 44 years, who performed WIP and non-WIP actions in a controlled VR environment. This process yielded 44,084 images: 24,300 images associated with WIP movements and 19,784 images corresponding to non-WIP actions. This balanced, binary-labeled dataset is a foundational resource for training and evaluating classification models that can automatically detect WIP events from motion capture data.

3.3 Method for Generating Image Representations From 3D Position Data

This section details the methods and experimental procedures employed to generate, visualize, and classify WIP movements.

To enable robust analysis of human movement, we transform raw 3D positional data into 2D image representations that capture the spatial and temporal properties of head and hand motions.

Assume a temporal sequence of N frames. For each frame i , we track the 3D coordinates of the head (\mathbf{p}_h), the right hand (\mathbf{p}_r), and the left hand (\mathbf{p}_l):

$$\mathbf{p}_h(i) = (x_h(i), y_h(i), z_h(i)) , \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{p}_r(i) = (x_r(i), y_r(i), z_r(i)) , \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{p}_l(i) = (x_l(i), y_l(i), z_l(i)) . \quad (4)$$

3.3.1 Coordinate Normalization and Scaling

We first normalize the raw coordinates to a unit range $[0, 1]$ based on their global minima and maxima:

$$x_{\min}, x_{\max}; \quad y_{\min}, y_{\max}; \quad z_{\min}, z_{\max} . \quad (5)$$

For each coordinate:

$$\hat{x}(i) = \frac{x(i) - x_{\min}}{x_{\max} - x_{\min}} , \quad (6)$$

$$\hat{y}(i) = \frac{y(i) - y_{\min}}{y_{\max} - y_{\min}} , \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{z}(i) = \frac{z(i) - z_{\min}}{z_{\max} - z_{\min}} . \quad (8)$$

We then scale these normalized values to discrete pixel indices according to the chosen image dimensions $W \times H \times D$. Here, W and H represent the width and height for the frontal-plane representation, and D is the depth dimension for the additional plane:

$$X(i) = \lfloor \hat{x}(i) \cdot W \rfloor + 1 , \quad (9)$$

$$Y(i) = \lfloor \hat{y}(i) \cdot H \rfloor + 1 , \quad (10)$$

$$Z(i) = \lfloor \hat{z}(i) \cdot D \rfloor + 1 . \quad (11)$$

To prevent out-of-bound indexing, we clamp the values of $X(i), Y(i), Z(i)$ to their respective maxima.

3.3.2 Image Construction

Two distinct 2D images are generated for each frame:

1. **Planar Image (XY-Plane):** A binary mask of size $H \times W$ is constructed:

$$I_{XY}(y', x'; i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } (x', y') \in \{(X_h(i), Y_h(i)), (X_r(i), Y_r(i)), (X_l(i), Y_l(i))\} , \\ 0 & \text{otherwise .} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

2. **Depth-Integrated Image (YZ or XZ-Plane):** To incorporate depth-related variation, a second binary mask of size $H \times D$ is created:

$$I_{YZ}(y', z'; i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } (y', z') \in \{(Y_h(i), Z_h(i)), (Y_r(i), Z_r(i)), (Y_l(i), Z_l(i))\} , \\ 0 & \text{otherwise .} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

These two images are then concatenated to form a combined representation of frontal and depth dynamics.

3.3.3 Temporal Smoothing and Trajectory Visualization

To represent motion trajectories and minimize noise, we maintain a buffer of the most recent M frames:

$$I_{XY}^{(\text{traj})}(y', x'; i) = \max_{j \in \{i-M, \dots, i\}} I_{XY}(y', x'; j) , \quad (14)$$

$$I_{YZ}^{(\text{traj})}(y', z'; i) = \max_{j \in \{i-M, \dots, i\}} I_{YZ}(y', z'; j). \quad (15)$$

This accumulation highlights repetitive motion patterns and smoothing effects, providing richer information for downstream analysis.

3.3.4 Labeling and Output

Finally, each image is labeled based on the participant’s action during the corresponding frame interval—e.g., “WIP” vs. “non-WIP”—and stored as a standard PNG file. These labeled images collectively form the dataset, which is then split such that 80% of the images are used to train the classification models, and the remaining 20% are reserved for testing. The split was performed randomly across the entire dataset, ensuring a representative mix of data from all participants in both the training and testing sets. While this approach prioritizes overall data diversity, it does not isolate individual participants between training and testing, making it suitable for evaluating the model’s general performance across mixed-participant scenarios.

In summary, the described procedure converts raw 3D positional data into 2D image representations that encode both frontal and depth-related motion features, providing a flexible and interpretable framework for analyzing human movement patterns in VR environments.

3.4 Neural Network Architectures

In this work, we compare two approaches for classifying WIP: (1) conventional artificial neural networks based on the MLP model, and (2) a neuromorphic architecture using a RAF spiking neural network. Specifically, we constructed both ANNs and SNNs by designing the necessary input/output interfaces and implementing varying numbers of hidden layers. Our goal was to identify the minimal depth and number of neurons per

hidden layer capable of achieving over **95%** accuracy on the WIP classification task while maintaining computational efficiency.

Each network comprises three layers:

- **Input layer:** Accepts an input vector corresponding to the pixel intensities of the WIP images.
- **Hidden layer:** Contains the neural units for each model configuration.
- **Output layer:** Produces two outputs representing the WIP and non-WIP classes.

Although we focus on minimal network architectures, the exact number of neurons in the hidden layer depends on the model type and activation function. To explore different configurations, we propose four models:

- **RAF-1:** One Resonate-and-Fire neuron.
- **MLP-1-ReLU:** One perceptron using the Rectified Linear Unit activation function.
- **MLP-2-Tanh:** Two perceptrons, each employing the hyperbolic tangent activation function.
- **MLP-4-Sigmoid:** Four perceptrons, with Sigmoid activation function.

Models **RAF-1** and **MLP-1-ReLU** emphasize simplicity by using a single neuron in their hidden layer, effectively processing the input while minimizing network depth. **MLP-2-Tanh** increases representational capacity by introducing an additional perceptrons, whereas **MLP-4-Sigmoid** further deepens the network to capture more complex patterns. Understanding each model’s neuron requirements allows us to optimize performance for various applications, particularly real-time scenarios where computational efficiency and high detection accuracy are paramount.

Our methodology involves training and evaluating all four models to ensure robust, real-time classification of WIP states. By systematically comparing these architectures, we aim to balance the trade-off between model complexity and the reliability of WIP detection.

3.4.1 Uploading Images to Networks

For ANNs composed of MLPs, the images are first flattened into vectors, and the ReLU activation function is applied to these values.

In contrast, for SNNs composed of RAF neurons, referred to as RAF-based models, the images are encoded into Poisson-distributed spike trains. In this encoding scheme, the intensity of each pixel determines the spike event rate, a widely adopted practice in SNN implementations [33, 34].

4 Results

This section details the outcomes of training and evaluating the four models on the WIP detection task, highlighting key performance metrics, robustness to noise, and computational efficiency.

4.1 Accuracy Comparison

The models achieved excellent classification accuracies, with the RAF-1 model reaching 98.57%, marginally outperformed by the MLP configurations MLP-1-ReLU: 99.87%; MLP-2-Tanh: 99.83%; MLP-4-Sigmoid: 99.81%. While MLP-based models attained slightly higher accuracies, the RAF-1 model offered unique advantages, including reduced complexity and interpretable parameters, such as the resonance frequency, which directly informs the discrimination between WIP and non-WIP actions.

The neural network models were trained using a random initialization of weights, ensuring variability in learning dynamics. Each model was trained for a maximum of 150 epochs, employing an adaptive learning rate schedule with an initial learning rate of 0.001 and a reduction factor of 0.9 applied after 10 epochs of stagnation in validation performance. This setup ensures convergence and avoids overfitting while facilitating a fair comparison across models. Table 1 summarizes the fixed hyperparameters used across all models. Furthermore, to achieve optimal performance for the RAF-1 model, we selected $\xi = 3.4$, $\omega = 1.4$, and $v_{th} = 0.6$ as its hyperparameters.

Notably, the results of the MLP-based models surpass the accuracy reported in [20], where their model achieved 99.32%. While a direct comparison is inherently limited due to differences in datasets and experimental setups, the performance of the MLP-based approaches demonstrates an advancement over prior state-of-the-art results. Our development with MLP-based models not only achieved higher accuracy but also maintained robustness and strong generalization capabilities, underscoring their suitability for the WIP detection task.

# Layers	Batch-size	Loss	LR-init
1	512	nll	0.001
LR-factor	LR-patience	LR-min	Weight-decay
0.9	10	1×10^{-14}	5×10^{-7}

Table 1: Fixed model hyperparameters. nll stands for negative log-likelihood.

4.2 Noise Robustness Analysis

To evaluate robustness, we introduced additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) during testing, with noise levels ranging from 0.5 to 4 standard deviations in increments of 0.5. AWGN serves as an effective proxy for real-world VR noise because it mimics common sources of variability, such as random drift, sensor jitter, and environmental interference, that often affect motion tracking devices.

The RAF-1 model demonstrated superior resilience, maintaining 85.09% accuracy at one standard deviation, compared to 74.67% (MLP-1-ReLU), 73.78% (MLP-2-Tanh), and 69.71% (MLP-4-Sigmoid). This robustness is attributed to the resonance property of RAF neurons, which enhances signal-to-noise differentiation. As noise

increased to two standard deviations, accuracies decreased, with RAF-1 still leading at 71.31% compared to the next best model, MLP-1-ReLU, at 64.55%. Figure 3 illustrates the comparative performance of the models under various noise levels.

Fig. 3: Impact of additive white Gaussian noise during testing comparing MLP-based models with the RAF-based model.

4.3 Computational Efficiency

The computational efficiency of the models was evaluated in terms of training time. MLP-based models (MLP-1-ReLU, MLP-2-Tanh, and MLP-4-Sigmoid) demonstrated similar training times, averaging 5.10 seconds per iteration on our server (Section 3.1). In contrast, the RAF-1 model required 7.25 seconds per iteration, representing a 42.5% increase in training time. This additional time is attributed to the need for tuning neuronal parameters such as ξ (damping factor), ω (resonance frequency), and v_{th} (threshold potential).

Despite the longer training phase, the RAF model exhibits significant advantages in energy efficiency and computational cost during inference. The spike-based communication mechanism inherent to the RAF architecture reduces the number of operations required for classification, making it particularly suitable for deployment in resource-constrained VR devices.

4.4 Summary of Findings

Our results reveal the following key insights:

1. **High Accuracy with Minimal Complexity:** Despite its simplicity, the RAF-1 model achieved competitive accuracy levels, highlighting the effectiveness of neuromorphic architectures for WIP detection.
2. **Noise Robustness:** The RAF model outperformed MLP-based models under noisy conditions, demonstrating its potential for deployment in real-world VR systems where sensor data is often imperfect.
3. **Efficient Resource Utilization:** The RAF architecture’s reduced computational requirements make it an ideal candidate for low-latency, high-performance VR applications.

5 Participant Study: Comparative Experiment

In order to assess and compare the WIP techniques presented in this paper with traditional navigation methods in terms of usability and participant acceptance, we conducted a controlled experiment with **30 participants**. Three primary methods of navigation were evaluated:

- **Teleport:** Participants point the controller at a target location and instantly teleport to that spot.
- **WIP-NN:** The walking-in-place (WIP) method introduced in this paper, encoding positional data into 2D images to feed a neural network.
- **WIP-head:** A simple WIP technique relying predominantly on head-position thresholds to identify stepping motions, inspired by [20].

All participants experienced the same virtual environment, navigating freely within a scenario depicting an urban garden square with social activity—restaurants, bars, and multiple non-playable characters (NPCs) walking and interacting. Figure 4 provides a screenshot of this virtual setting. Each participant tested all three locomotion methods in a counterbalanced order, with equivalent exposure times to mitigate potential learning effects.

The participants were mainly women in their early 20s, University students, with low levels of computer programming knowledge and computer game playing. Details of the sample are shown in Table S1 included in the supplementary material.

The experiment was approved by the *Comisió de Bioètica de la Universitat de Barcelona*, and all procedures were carried out in accordance with the approved protocol. Participants provided written and informed consent and were informed that they could leave the experiment at any time without giving a reason or losing any benefits. Each participant received 15 euros as compensation for their participation in the experiment.

Fig. 4: Screenshot of the VR scenario used in the experiment.

5.1 Methods

After completing each VR experience, participants answered the questions shown in Table 2. At the conclusion, they provided an overall ranking (1 = most preferred, 3 = least preferred) and open-ended comments about what they liked or disliked.

Table 2: Questionnaire response variables after each experience

Variable	Meaning (Spanish)	Meaning (English)
comfort	Califique su sensación de comodidad utilizando el sistema de desplazamiento. 1. Incómodo ... 7. Muy cómodo	Rate your feeling of comfort using the displacement system. 1. Uncomfortable ... 7. Very comfortable
dizziness	Califique la sensación de mareo utilizando el sistema de desplazamiento. 1. Ningún mareo ... 7. Mucho mareo	Rate the feeling of dizziness using the displacement system. 1. No sickness ... 7. A lot of sickness
functionality	¿Ha funcionado correctamente el sistema de navegación de acuerdo a sus movimientos? 1. Fallaba mucho ... 7. Reaccionaba correctamente	Has the navigation system worked correctly according to your movements? 1. Failed a lot ... 7. Responded correctly

Figure 5 shows the boxplots of the results for these questions. Teleportation appears to have the most comfort and the least dizziness amongst the conditions. WIP-head has the worst comfort and functionality. With respect to functionality the difference between Teleportation and WIP-NN is small – the difference in median is 1 and the IQRs overlap considerably.

From this descriptive analysis, we would conclude that the most ‘convenient’ method of locomotion is Teleportation since, on average, it is the ‘best’ among the three methods. Still, if a method is required to be like ‘walking’ then the WIP-NN is preferable.

Fig. 5: Box charts showing Comfort, Dizziness and Functionality for each method.

5.1.1 Sentiment Analysis

After each of the 3 methods, participants were asked to write comments:

- Spanish version: *Por favor, escriba sus comentarios. Las cosas que podrías considerar son: Funcionamiento, sensaciones, ...*
- English version: *Please write your comments. Things you might consider are: Functionality, feelings, ...*

The essays were written in English and Spanish but they were all translated into English. We used the Hugging Face system with the BERT model to find sentiment associated with the comments that people wrote [35]. This method estimates sentiment with a score (‘star’) between 1 (lowest) and 5 (highest) sentiment. By ‘high sentiment’ we mean positive emotions or attitudes, whereas low represents negative emotions or attitudes.

Figure 6 shows that the greatest median sentiment is for the Teleportation method (median 4 out of a maximum of 5) followed again by the WIP-NN method, with considerable overlap of the IQR with Teleportation, and with the WIP-head method with the lowest sentiment.

In Table S2 included in the Supplementary Material, we randomly choose up to 3 phrases from the various star categories to get some idea about the meaning of these sentiment scores.

5.2 Statistical Analysis

Let y_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ be the i th observation on any of the response variables (comfort, dizziness, functionality). $N = 90$ is the total number of observations, but each individual has 3 observations. We are interested in the effect of the condition on the response variable, taking into account the repeated measures.

The linear predictor is:

$$\eta_i = \mu + \gamma_{\text{par}[i]} + \alpha_{C[i]} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N$$

Fig. 6: Box plots showing the means and standard errors of the number of stars (sentiment) for the 3 conditions.

where $\text{par}[i]$ is of the form $0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1, \dots, n, n, n = 29$ representing the participants and γ_j is the effect of the j th participant.

$C[i]$ represents the conditions:

$$C[i] = \{0, \text{Teleportation}; 1, \text{WIP-head}; 2, \text{WIP-NN}\}$$

Therefore, α_0 , α_1 , and α_2 are the effects of the condition.

The response variables are ordinal (with values $1, 2, \dots, 7$), so an ordered logistic model is appropriate. In this specific case the relationship between the response variable and the linear predictor η_i is:

$$\log \left(\frac{y_i > j}{y_i \leq j} \right) = \eta_i - c_j, \quad j = 1, \dots, k - 1$$

Here there are ordered categories $1, 2, \dots, k = 7$. The c_j are ordered cut-points estimated from the data, with normal prior distributions with means $-3, -2, \dots, 3$ and standard deviation 1.5.

The prior distributions used are:

$$\alpha_1, \gamma_j \text{ normal}(\text{mean} = 0, \text{standard deviation} = 1)$$

These are weakly informative priors [36] that allow the data to dominate the posterior distributions.

All three variables, comfort, dizziness, and functionality, can be included in the same overall model. We can also include 'stars' from the sentiment analysis in the same model, except that the number of ordinal values is $k = 5$.

For identifiability, we need to set the first value of each parameter to 0 so that, for example, $\alpha_0 = 0$, and therefore α_1 and α_2 are offsets from this. In other words,

the Teleport condition is the baseline, and we are considering the WIP conditions as offsets from that.

We used PyMC in Python [37] to obtain the posterior distributions of the parameters. Of interest are the α_j since these indicate the impact of the condition.

Table 3 summarises the posterior distributions. Considering the HDIs - for comfort, it is clear that both WIP-head and WIP-NN have smaller values than Teleportation (consistent with the Comfort box chart in Figure 5). However, the 95% HDI for WIP-head is lower than for WIP-NN, even though there is a small overlap.

For dizziness, their HDIs indicate that both WIP methods are greater than Teleport, and the HDIs are approximately the same. So the WIP methods are associated with slightly greater dizziness, but there is no difference between them. This accords with the Dizziness box chart in Figure 5.

For functionality, the results are similar to comfort and accord with the Functionality box chart in Figure 5.

For stars, the result is the same again, in accord with Figure 6.

Table 3: Summaries of the posterior distributions of the model parameters. HDI refers to the 95% highest density interval (the smallest interval containing 95% of the probability density).

Parameter	Meaning	Mean	SD	HDI 2.5%	HDI 97.5%
Comfort					
μ		2.947	0.779	1.424	4.498
α_0	Teleport	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
α_1	WIP-head	-3.803	0.672	-5.122	-2.520
α_2	WIP-NN	-1.783	0.532	-2.890	-0.793
Dizziness					
μ		-3.945	0.950	-5.880	-2.172
α_0	Teleport	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
α_1	WIP-head	1.034	0.701	-0.161	2.443
α_2	WIP-NN	1.427	0.753	-0.033	2.765
Functionality					
μ		3.721	0.827	2.235	5.484
α_0	Teleport	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
α_1	WIP-head	-4.116	0.700	-5.486	-2.780
α_2	WIP-NN	-1.919	0.565	-3.041	-0.851
Stars					
μ		2.522	0.869	0.873	4.234
α_0	Teleport	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
α_1	WIP-head	-3.626	0.674	-5.005	-2.408
α_2	WIP-NN	-0.988	0.500	-1.953	-0.046

From the posterior distributions it is also possible to compute overall probabilities that the results for any condition are greater than for any other condition.

These comparisons are shown in Table 4, where we can see again that Teleport gives the best outcome in all cases.

Table 4: Probabilities of condition comparisons

	Pr(Tele > WIP-head)	Pr(WIP-head > WIP-NN)	Pr(WIP-NN > Tele)
Comfort	1.000	0.000	0.001
Dizziness	0.061	0.204	0.985
Functionality	1.000	0.001	0.000
Stars	1.000	0.000	0.018

Comparing WIP-head with Teleport, the probability that WIP-head results in greater dizziness is 0.939. Moreover, $\text{Pr}(\text{WIP-head} > \text{WIP-NN}) = 0.204$, meaning that there is a 0.806 probability that WIP-NN results in less dizziness. With respect to comfort, functionality and stars, WIP-NN has a probability close to 1 in each case of being greater than WIP-head.

The conclusion is that if participants simply need to move from one location to another then Teleport is the best method. However, if for other reasons a locomotion method is needed that simulates walking (e.g., to avoid disorientation) then the WIP-NN is preferred to the simple form of WIP provided by moving the head above and below a given threshold.

5.3 Post Experience Measures

5.3.1 Ranking:

After experiencing the 3 conditions, participants were asked to rank the navigation methods:

- Spanish version: “¿Qué método de navegación elegiría para navegar por el escenario? Ordene los métodos de navegación por orden donde 1 es el mejor y 3 sería el peor.”
- English version: “Which navigation method would you choose to navigate the scenario? Rank the navigation methods in order, with 1 being the best and 3 being the worst.”

Table 5: Median and IQR of the ranks

Method	Median (25th–75th percentile)
Teleportation	1 (1 – 1)
WIP-head	3 (3 – 3)
WIP-NN	2 (2 – 2)

Table 5 shows the medians and IQRs of the ranks. The result overwhelmingly supports the previous conclusion that Teleportation is ranked the highest, followed by WIP-NN, with WIP-head lowest.

5.3.2 Sentiment Analysis

Following the ranking, participants were asked:

- Spanish version: “*Por favor, escriba el por qué de su elección.*”
- English version: “*Please write the reason for your choice.*”

Table 6: Frequency table of the number of stars

Stars	Frequency	%
1	0	0
2	1	3
3	16	53
4	12	40
5	1	3

Table 6 shows the frequency table indicating that the majority had middle sentiment levels but 43% high sentiment (4 or 5).

Finally, Table S3, included in the Supplementary Material, shows some randomly selected phrases associated with the various sentiment levels. This supports the analysis above that Teleportation is generally preferred for comfort and ease of use, but among the two WIP methods, the WIP-NN is preferred.

6 Discussion

Our findings demonstrate that converting head-and-hand motion data into 2D image representations significantly simplifies the WIP classification process. This transformation allows minimal neural network architectures to achieve high accuracy while reducing computational overhead. Notably, neuromorphic computing, exemplified by the RAF-1 model, emerged as a particularly robust and efficient approach for WIP discrimination, demonstrating resilience to varying levels of noise. Such robustness is particularly significant in real-world VR applications, where sensor data is frequently imperfect due to participant variability, device constraints, or environmental interference.

One of the key contributions of this study is the evaluation of the trade-off between training complexity and inference efficiency. While the neuromorphic RAF-1 model demands more extensive training—primarily due to the parameter tuning required for spiking neurons—it compensates with lower energy consumption and enhanced real-time suitability. These features are especially critical for standalone VR devices, where battery life and low-latency processing are paramount. Moreover, the biologically inspired architecture of RAF-1 enables efficient temporal feature extraction and maintains performance even under challenging conditions, making it a compelling solution for portable VR systems.

In terms of participant acceptance and navigation preferences, the data corroborate prior research wherein Teleport-style navigation is considered both efficient and comfortable for most participants ([16, 17]). Although it sacrifices some sense of continuous locomotion, its reduced susceptibility to motion sickness makes it particularly attractive to broader audiences. However, a significant drawback of teleportation,

particularly relevant for tasks requiring spatial understanding and navigation within complex environments, is its potential to impair wayfinding and induce spatial disorientation [38, 39]. Users may struggle to build accurate cognitive maps of the virtual space when relying solely on discontinuous jumps.

In contrast, our walking-in-place approach (WIP-NN) offered improved realism over Teleport and surpassed the head-threshold method (WIP-head), a well-known and popular method for WIP discrimination, in terms of comfort and functionality despite yielding slightly higher dizziness reports than Teleport for some participants. This suggests that for applications where maintaining spatial orientation and a sense of continuous presence is paramount, and where discontinuous methods like teleportation are unsuitable due to disorientation concerns, methods like the proposed WIP-NN offer a preferable alternative, especially favored by participants who prioritize a more naturalistic walking experience. The WIP-head method, requiring pronounced head-bobbing, demonstrated lower performance and was often described as tedious or misaligned with real stepping behavior, further positioning the WIP-NN technique as a more viable continuous locomotion alternative.

It is important to contextualize WIP within the broader spectrum of VR locomotion. As established by Usoh *et al.* [7], physically walking within the tracking space (“real walking”) provides the highest degree of presence and naturalness when feasible. Modern HMDs increasingly utilize inside-out tracking based on cameras and computer vision (like the Meta Quest 3 used in our data collection [32]), which accurately map the physical environment and enable room-scale real walking experiences. However, virtual environments often exceed the available physical space. WIP, therefore, serves as a crucial complementary technique. It does not necessarily exclude real walking; instead, a hybrid approach is highly practical, allowing users to physically walk to the boundary of their tracked area and seamlessly transition to WIP to continue navigating the larger virtual world. This combination leverages the benefits of real walking within the available space while enabling exploration beyond its physical limits using an intuitive, embodied method like WIP.

Another relevant technique is Redirected Walking (RDW), which subtly manipulates the virtual world’s mapping relative to the physical space, guiding users on curved paths physically while they perceive themselves walking straight virtually, thus enabling exploration of larger virtual spaces within smaller physical ones [40]. While powerful, RDW requires sufficient physical space to apply the redirection gains effectively and can introduce its complexities. Notably, RDW and WIP are not mutually exclusive. Research has explored combining these techniques, potentially using WIP when subtle redirection is insufficient or when the user approaches boundaries where RDW cannot be safely applied [41, 42]. Our focus on optimizing WIP detection provides a robust component that could potentially be integrated into such sophisticated hybrid locomotion systems that might also incorporate RDW and real walking.

Despite its advantages, this study also identifies opportunities for further research. Expanding dataset diversity to include a broader range of participant behaviors, body types, and VR hardware would enhance model generalizability. Additionally, rigorous testing in real-world scenarios, where unpredictable noise sources are common, is

essential to validate the model’s practical robustness. Finally, exploring hybrid architectures that integrate the strengths of MLP-based models with those of neuromorphic paradigms could yield solutions that balance accuracy, efficiency, and interpretability.

The implications of this work extend beyond WIP detection. The demonstrated ability to classify movement patterns with lightweight neural architectures has potential applications in real-time motion analysis for diverse VR use cases, including interactive gaming, immersive training, and therapeutic interventions. Furthermore, the biologically inspired design principles underlying the RAF-1 model align with the broader goals of sustainable and energy-efficient AI systems. By bridging biologically inspired computing with real-world VR challenges, this study offers a promising framework for more immersive, efficient, and accessible virtual environments.

7 Conclusions

As VR technology continues to advance, integrating natural movement techniques like WIP is essential for enhancing participant engagement, accessibility, and overall immersion. The ability to simulate walking motions without requiring extensive physical space has profound implications across various domains, including gaming, education, and therapy. This innovation promises to revolutionize how we interact with digital environments, making WIP essential for future VR applications.

However, the reliable discrimination of WIP states presents unique challenges that demand precision for several reasons. First, accurate detection ensures an immersive experience by minimizing sensorimotor incongruence. Second, precise classification is vital for real-time motion tracking, which sustains many VR applications requiring instantaneous feedback. Third, the ability to robustly differentiate WIP from other movements is critical for algorithmic adaptability, enabling systems to learn and tailor experiences to individual participants. Thus, achieving precision in WIP discrimination is a fundamental requirement for advancing movement-based VR systems.

To address these challenges, this study used 2D image encoding of positional data from the head, left hand, and right hand to preserve key motion features across multiple frames. This dataset was evaluated using both traditional AI models based on MLPs and neuromorphic approaches represented by spiking neural networks, specifically the RAF model.

Interestingly, the architectures required to achieve high performance were significantly less complex than anticipated, consisting of single-layer networks with only a few units. Our results demonstrate that neuromorphic approaches outperform MLPs in noisy environments, where aberrant conditions often lead to participant disorientation, frustration, and a diminished sense of presence. By leveraging the spike-based communication and biologically inspired design of RAF neurons, the neuromorphic model proved more resilient to sensor noise, making it a viable option for real-world deployment.

From the study evaluating different locomotion methods (Teleport, WIP-NN, and WIP-head), we draw the following conclusions:

- **WIP-NN improves upon WIP-head** by enhancing step detection, reducing frustration, and providing a more fluid sense of “in-place” walking.

- **Teleport remains the most preferred method**, consistently rating highest in comfort and functionality, with minimal dizziness.
- Hybrid solutions that combine Teleport’s reduced sickness with the immersive qualities of WIP-based methods could potentially meet a broader range of participant needs.

Future work will focus on validating these findings in more diverse and challenging scenarios, including environments where positional tracking data is incomplete or unreliable. Specifically, cross-validating the models with a larger and more diverse participant base will ensure robustness across different populations and VR hardware setups. Additionally, we aim to benchmark the performance of the RAF model in on-device deployment scenarios, utilizing the Meta Quest 3 hardware to assess its real-time efficiency and energy consumption under practical constraints.

We also aim to refine the neuromorphic approach by optimizing the number of units and tuning neuronal parameters to strike a balance between computational efficiency and performance. Ultimately, our goal is to develop a comprehensive library of neural networks tailored to recognize a wide range of VR activities and states, advancing the accessibility and functionality of VR technology.

Acknowledgements. Funded by the European Union (Grant agreement No 101057429). Complementary funding was received by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government’s Horizon Europe funding guarantee (10131373 and 10038599) and the National Key R&D Program of the Ministry of Science and Technology of China (MOST 2023YFE0199700). Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA), UKRI, or MOST.

Neither the European Union nor HADEA nor UKRI nor MOST can be held responsible for them.

Author Contributions. The conception and design of the study were carried out by J.G., and M.S. Material preparation, data collection, and analysis were performed by J.G., D.B., and M.S. The technical implementation was carried out by J.G., D.B., and R.O. The first draft of the manuscript was written by J.G. and D.B., and all authors provided feedback on previous versions. Review and editing were performed by M.S. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Data Availability. Data availability The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Declarations

Conflict of interest. The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Ethical Approval. The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Institutional Review Board of the University of Barcelona (IRB No: 00003099).

Informed Consent. Informed consent was obtained from all participants involved in this study. Participants were provided with details about the purpose, procedures, potential risks/benefits, and confidentiality measures of the research before data collection. They gave their consent voluntarily to participate.

Supplementary information. This article includes supplementary files.

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Supplementary Material

Table S1: Characteristics of the Sample

Variable	Meaning	Result
sex	0: Male 1: Female	Male: 7, Female: 23
age	Age in years (mean \pm SD)	24.23 \pm 5.33
occupation	0: Full-time employment 1: Student 2: Part-time employment 3: Self-employed	0: 5 1: 21 2: 3 3: 1
education	0: University 1: Secondary Education 2: Vocational Education	0: 28 1: 1 2: 1
computing	Level of computing: 1 None ... 7 Expert Median (interquartile range)	5 (1)
vr	Prior VR Experience: 1 None ... 7 A lot Median (interquartile range)	3 (2)
programming	Computer programming experience: 1 None ... 7 A lot Median (interquartile range)	2 (1)
gamesyear	Times playing computer games in the last year: 0: 0 times 1: 1–5 times 2: 6–10 times 3: 11–15 times 4: 16–20 times 5: 21–25 times 6: More than 25 times Median (interquartile range)	1 (4)
gamesweek	Hours playing computer games in the past week: 0: 0 hours 1: 1–2 hours 2: 3–4 hours 3: 5–6 hours 4: 7–8 hours 5: 9–10 hours 6: More than 10 hours Median (interquartile range)	0 (1)

Table S2: Randomly selected phrases in the sentiment classes

Rating	Phrase
1 star	<p>1. There are places I could not access. (Teleport)</p> <p>2. At one point the blue icon to move disappeared, and red arrows appeared, but after moving it appeared again. (Teleport)</p>
2 stars	<p>1. The movement wasn't going very well, as it looked not very fluid. I had to take very big steps for the avatar to move, and taking small steps it would stay still for a long time (the movement was slow and difficult to control). Also, this type of movement generates motion sickness for me so I couldn't use an application that had it as the only option. (WIP-head)</p> <p>2. It wasn't fluid and I could barely move. To take a step I needed to make a lot of gestures and even then I couldn't move. As for sensations, it was fine, without any dizziness, but it was frustrating to see how I tried to move and couldn't. (WIP head)</p> <p>3. The movement was not smooth and I had the feeling of stopping almost every step. (WIP head)</p> <p>4. It wasn't fluid, it went in jerks and didn't always react to movements (WIP-head)</p> <p>5. It was noticeably not fluid and gave the feeling that it was getting stuck. Also, there were times when it didn't identify my movement. (WIP-head)</p>
3 stars	<p>1. Greater fluidity in movement, it was more natural and real. (WIP-NN)</p> <p>2. More comfortable than the first but lots of dizziness. (WIP-NN)</p> <p>3. I don't feel that it went very smoothly, the feeling is that how I move and the response of Virtual Reality do not fully agree. (WIP-head)</p> <p>4. It was a bit strange when I was trying to change direction. (WIP-NN)</p> <p>5. The pattern of movement was not always the same, at times it went faster than at others, despite not changing the rhythm of my leg and arm movements. (WIP-NN)</p>
4 stars	<p>1. I would define it as very intuitive. (Teleport)</p> <p>2. The system allowed me to move around the scene as I moved on site, without getting stuck and in a fluid way. It gave me the feeling that I was walking naturally through the city that appeared in the scene. (WIP-NN)</p> <p>3. I could move without problem to the point I wanted without much difficulty. I didn't have a sensation of dizziness, it even seemed like a simpler system of movement within the space, it's a system that responds quickly to the trigger stimulus. (Teleport)</p> <p>4. The operation has been correct, I saw it fluid, you could only tell you were in virtual reality from the more robotic movements, but very well achieved. (WIP-NN)</p> <p>5. It went very well and I also didn't have any feeling of disorientation or anything, quite fluid. (Teleport)</p>
5 stars	<p>1. It's my favorite of the 3. It's much easier to control in terms of location and distance of movement. It's faster and doesn't generate any discomfort (regarding motion sickness). I also consider that, in the virtual world, it is realistic since teleporting like this doesn't take away realism from the experience. You gain in control, precision, time... (Teleport)</p> <p>2. Very good immersion, both visual and auditory. (WIP-NN)</p> <p>3. Very easy to move around and how not having to move. (Teleport)</p> <p>4. Very realistic feeling, very fluid movements and comfort. (Teleport)</p> <p>5. For me the most comfortable, it worked perfectly and did not give a feeling of dizziness, it's also realistic because you can't go through walls. (Teleport)</p>

Table S3: Randomly selected phrases in the sentiment classes for the rank reasons

Rating	Phrase
1 star	1. N/A
2 stars	1. The two walking in place seem similar to me. I would use them if they allowed me to move faster. This way I wouldn't use them.
3 stars	<p>1. The Teleport is more comfortable to use because it doesn't involve your movement and there are no dizziness effects. In second place, the WIP-NN was comfortable because it advances quickly but I had a feeling of dizziness. And finally the "head" because it advances very little even if you make the effort to walk.</p> <p>2. The teleport has been very comfortable to use, very skillful and super fast. The WIP-NN has been a bit more choppy, but it has also had quite fast and comfortable movement. The walking in place head has been the worst in relation to the other two, it has gone with many interruptions, it hasn't been fluid, I've barely been able to move...</p> <p>3. Because I used parts of my body and that's why it seemed more realistic to me, I felt more immersed in the virtual reality world.</p> <p>4. With the last experiment I felt more comfortable, therefore I really liked the order that was proposed, teleport doesn't seem pleasant to me because only a light is used to be able to interact and it doesn't allow more parts of the body to intervene in the experiment.</p> <p>5. I felt more comfortable with the teleport because the movements were faster, however the WIP-NN seems more realistic to me.</p>
4 stars	<p>1. The teleport works much faster and more efficiently than the walking in place options, since the latter worked more slowly, with the walking in place head being the worst (greater slowness and the walking was choppy).</p> <p>2. It is more comfortable, fast and useful for moving around.</p> <p>3. Teleport seems the most comfortable and precise to me for moving around and investigating well, the second is better than the third but still it's not as fluid as the teleport.</p> <p>4. The WIP-NN could have been the best if there had been more convergence with real-world gestures, and if I had gotten used to walking without moving until it stopped seeming unnatural. Even so, the teleport has been the one that seemed best to me of the options, although it included the marker. Perhaps a more discreet marker could break less the sense of immersion.</p> <p>5. The teleport has been the most comfortable for me since I didn't have to make many movements to be able to move around the virtual space. The WIP-NN is much more interactive than the teleport but due to the small feeling of dizziness that I experienced, I have put it in second place, but to me it seems more interesting that it's more interactive.</p>
5 stars	1. I put the teleport in first place for the speed of movement as well as fluidity.